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Research Article

Therapeutic Evaluation of *Nyctanthes Arbor-Tristis* on Obsessive Compulsive Disorder

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ABSTRACT

Obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) is a mental health condition where a person has obsessive thoughts and compulsive activity. OCD can impair all areas of brain functioning and produce devastating effects on patients and their families. Marble-burying behavior of mice is a well-accepted paradigm to screen anti-compulsive activity. The aim of present study was to evaluate the anti-obsessive compulsive effect of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* extract in mice. The present investigation revealed a significant decrease in marble-burying behavior of mice after oral administration of EENAT (200 and 400 mg/kg) and exhibit anti OCD like effect and the effect of EENAT was comparable to standard anti OCD drug Fluoxetine which also reduce the marble burying behavior in accordance with the previous findings. The maximum effective dose of EENAT was 200mg/kg, at which there was no change in the motor activity. The dose of 400mg/kg also exhibited inhibitory effect on marble burying behavior, but it also reduced the motor activity, hence it is not clear whether the effect of EENAT at 400mg/kg it is due to inhibition of motor activity. The experimental results of this study shows that ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* possess anti-obsessive compulsive activities.

INTRODUCTION

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis (NAT), also known as Parijata or Harsinghar is an Indian traditional plant of great importance. It has been used in Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani system of medicine for treatment of various infectious and non-infectious diseases. Each part of the plant has some medicinal

value and is used for various pharmacological actions.[1] *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* has been used for centuries in Ayurvedic medicine, either alone or in combination with other herbs, as a memory and learning enhancer, sedative, anti-epileptic, antidepressant and antianxiety.[2] Animal studies of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* whole plant or alcohol extracts have reported cognition enhancing effects

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including improved motor learning and acquisition, consolidation, and retention of memory.[3] which suggests that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* influences various neurotransmitter systems including serotonergic system.[4] Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is characterized by persistent ritualistic thoughts (obsession) which are ego-diatomic and associated with seemingly purposeful behaviors (compulsions). [5] Its comorbidity with major depression is often evident, and it is considered as an anxiety disorder.[6] Potent serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are consistently effective in patients of obsessive-compulsive disorder which indicates that serotonin dysfunction is the underlying cause in OCD.[7] An outgrowing research has been done in pharmacotherapy of OCD but research into effective herbal treatments for OCD has just started. Those plants which are used to treat anxiety and depression can be a potential therapeutic strategy for treatment of OCD. [8] Evidences shows that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* may be useful in the treatment of obsessive-compulsive disorder. Therefore, the influence of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* was investigated on the marble-burying behavior of mice a well-accepted model of obsessive-compulsive behavior, due to its high face and predictive validity. [9]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and identification of plant materials:

The plant of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* collected was from the medicinal garden of Vidyabharati college of pharmacy. Identified and authenticated by Prof. Kajal Apale Department of Botany, Vidyabharati Mahavidyalaya, Amravati.

The flowers of Preparation of plant extract:

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis was collected from healthy plants, cleaned properly, and dried at

shade at room temperature. The dried plant materials were finely powdered and macerated thrice with 80% (v/v) ethanol in shaking condition for 7 days at room temperature. The extract thus obtained were filtered and concentrated by air drying and stored at 4°C.

Drugs and administrations:

Fluoxetine hydrochloride was purchased from local market of Amravati, India. Ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* (EENAT) and Fluoxetine HCl were prepared in 0.9% saline. Fluoxetine HCl was administered orally. EENAT and saline were administered orally. All drug solutions were prepared fresh.

Selection of animal:

The Male Swiss albino mice (weighing 20-25g), were obtained from the animal house of department of Pharmacology, Vidyabharati college of Pharmacy, Amravati. All the animals were acclimatized to the animal house prior to use. They were kept in cages in animal house with a 12hr light: 12hr dark cycle at temperature (25±1°C) with 50±55% of relative humidity. Animals were fed on pellets and tap water ad libitum. The care and handling of mice were in accordance with the internationally accepted standard guideline for use of animals (CPCSEA). Experiments were performed in accordance with the committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experimental animals (CPCSEA) guidelines after the approval of the experimental protocol by the Institutional animals ethical committee (IAEC).

Phytochemical screening:

The crude extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening for their presence and absence of active phytoconstituents. [10]

Experimental design:

Mice were divided into different groups (n=6). EENAT (200, 400 mg/kg) p.o. fluoxetine(15 mg/kg). EENAT and fluoxetine were administered orally (p.o.) 30 min prior to the assessment of marble-burying behavior and locomotor activity. The control group received 0.9% saline (10 mL/kg, po). After 30 min, the marble-burying behavior and motor activity were assessed in separate groups.

Evaluation of Anti obsessive-compulsive activity:

Marble Burying Behavior

The marble burying test takes advantage of the mice's natural proclivity for digging in the natural settings (e.g., burrows and escape tunnels) and in standard cage bedding. Briefly, male mice were placed in a polypropylene cage (37 cm × 21cm x 14 cm) with 20 glass marbles (10 mm in diameter) that were evenly dispersed on 5 cm deep sawdust for 20min without access to food or drink. The testing cages were kept in a separate room from the housing area. The number of marbles buried at least 2/3 of the way within 20min was used to measure compulsive-like digging behavior recorded.[11]

Motor Activity By Actophotometer

The locomotor activity was measured using an actophotometer. The movement of the animal cuts off a beam light falling on the photocell and a count was recorded and displayed digitally. Motor activity was assessed in terms of total number of counts of light beam inter-ruptions in 10 min. An acquisition period of 5 min was given to each mouse before assessment of motor activity. [12]

Statistical Analysis:

The data were expressed as a mean ± SEM. Results were analyzed statistically by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnet test. Statistical significant was considered as P< 0.05 in all cases.

RESULTS

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening Phytochemical test of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Glycoside, Sterols, Terpenoids, Phenol, Tannin.

Table no.1: Phytochemical investigation of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

Sr. No.	Phytochemical analysis	Remark
1.	Alkaloids	(+)
2.	Flavonoids	(+)
3.	Glycoside	(+)
4.	Sterols	(+)
5.	Terpenoids	(+)
6.	Phenol	(+)
7.	Tannin	(+)
8.	Carbohydrate	(-)
9.	Protein	(-)

Effect of EENAT on marble burying behavior and motor activity:

One way ANOVA exhibited that EENAT significantly influenced marble burying behavior. The Dunnett's test showed that the EENAT, 200 and 400 mg/kg significantly reduced the number of marbles buried (Table no.2 and fig no. 1) Motor activity was not affected by EENAT at the dose of 200 and 400 mg/kg, however EENAT at a dose of 400mg/kg significantly suppressed the locomotor activity (Table no.3 and fig no. 2).

Marble burying behavior

Table no.2: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on marble burying behavior in mice.

Day/Group	Control (1ml/kg)	Fluoxetine (15mg/kg)	EENAT (200mg/kg)	EENAT (400mg/kg)
Day 1	11.333±0.333	5.333±0.211**	9.333±0.211*	6.500±0.224**
Day 7	13.333±0.333	3.333±0.211**	7.167±0.477*	5.500±0.224**
Day 14	13.500±0.428	2.333±0.211**	5.167±0.307*	3.500±0.224**

Each value represents the mean ± S.E.M (n=6). (*p<0.0001) compared with control and standard group.

Effect of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on marble burying behavior in mice.

Each value represents the mean ± S.E.M (n=6). (*p<0.0001) compared with control and standard group.

Figure 1. Effect of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on marble burying behavior in mice.

Motor activity:

Table no.3: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on motor activity in mice.

Day/Group	Control (1ml/kg)	Fluoxetine (15mg/kg)	EENAT (200mg/kg)	EENAT (400mg/kg)
Day 1	447.667±4.638	347.333±0.715**	386.500±0.885*	365.167±5.237*
Day 7	457.333±0.667	332.000±0.856**	367.333±3.879*	348.833±2.994*
Day 14	449.167±5.787	324.833±1.195**	342.833±3.135*	340.500±2.668*

Each value represents the mean ± S.E.M (n=6). (*p<0.0001) compared with control and standard group.

Each value represents the mean \pm S.E.M (n=6). (* $p < 0.0001$) compared with control and standard group.

Figure 2: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on motor activity in mice.

DISCUSSION

The results of the present investigations revealed that ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* exhibited anti obsessive-compulsive effect by inhibiting marble-burying behavior and it was comparable to that of fluoxetine.[13] The present investigation revealed a significant decrease in marble-burying behavior of mice after oral administration of EENAT (200 and 400 mg/kg) and exhibit anti OCD like effect and the effect of EENAT was comparable to standard anti OCD drug Fluoxetine (15 mg/kg) which also reduce the marble burying behavior in accordance with the previous findings. The maximum effective dose of EENAT was 200mg/kg, at which there was no change in the motor activity. The dose of 400mg/kg also exhibited inhibitory effect on marble burying behavior, but it also reduced the motor activity, hence it is not clear whether the effect of EENAT at 400mg/kg is perse effect or it due to inhibition of motor activity. The result of this study shows that ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* has positive effect on

obsession and compulsion and generalized anxiety in mice. OCD has been linked to abnormalities with the neurotransmitter serotonin, although it could be either a cause or an effect of these abnormalities. Serotonin is thought to have a role in regulating anxiety. It is hypothesized that the serotonin receptors of OCD sufferers may be relatively understimulated. OCD patients benefit from the use of SSRIs, a class of antidepressant medications that allow for more serotonin to be readily available to other nerve cells. [14] So, it can be assumed that ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* may have an identical effect to SSRI or some facilitatory effect on serotonergic neurotransmission. In the present study, phytochemical screening of ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* revealed the presence of flavonoids, steroids, saponins, tannins, terpenoids and phytosterols. So it is possible that the mechanism of anti-obsessive compulsive action of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* may be due to involvement of any of these phytoconstituents in serotonergic neurotransmission. Moreover, triterpenoids (steroidal compounds), which are able to cross blood brain barrier (BBB) due to their lipophilic nature, are present in *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. So, it can be assumed that such compounds might also be responsible to elicit anti-obsessive compulsive activity at a molecular level in central nervous system.

CONCLUSION

Ethanol extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* dose dependently attenuated marble-burying behavior in mice, and the effect was comparable to that shown by fluoxetine, a reference standard drug. The present study concludes that the ethanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* shows anti-obsessive compulsive (anti-OCD) effect in dose-dependent manner. Phytochemical screening of the extract has shown the presence of flavonoids, saponins and steroids, which may account for biological activities. In the same way, identification and isolation of major constituents responsible for the activity and precise anti-obsessive compulsive mechanisms need to be identified.

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